

New phenothiazine compounds with dyeing properties

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Some new phenothiazine derivatives with dyeing properties have been synthesised. With the help of a difunctional compound, 1,4-bisbromomethylbenzene (2), the framework of 1-amino-8-hydroxynaphthaline-3,5-bisulphonic acid (4) is introduced and its skeleton grafted with azo derivatives of some aromatic amines (6) to yield the azo dyes (7).

The present study intends to increase the already known range of azo dyes with phenothiazine nucleus¹ by synthesizing dyes in which the chromophore group is situated outside the phenothiazine nucleus. The range of reactions is presented in Scheme 1.

Results and Discussion

The diazo derivatives of the following aromatic amine were used : aniline, *p*-methoxyaniline, *o*-chloroaniline, *o*-aniline sulphonic acid and *p*-toluidine. Taking into account

the low reactivity of NH group in phenothiazine, the process of alkylation was carried out through the following special methods : (a) the alkylation in biphasic system with NaOH (15–50%) in the presence of a phase transfer catalyst², (b) the reaction with thallium ethoxide in benzene followed by the condensation with the halo derivative, (c) the reaction of phenothiazine with the halo derivative in bipolar non-protic solvent (DMAC, DMSO, HMPTA) in the presence of diazabicycloundecene (DBU) as a catalyst and (d) the reaction with KOH in acetone catalyzed by cetyl-

Ar = Ph, 2-ClC₆H₄, 2-SO₃HC₆H₄, 4-MeOC₆H₄, 4-MeC₆H₄

Scheme 1

tributylphosphonium bromide, $C_{16}H_{33}P^+Bu^3]Br^-$ (CTPB), followed by the treatment with the halogenised derivative.

The best yields were obtained in the cases of methods c, b, d, a amounting to 96, 94, 62 and 49% respectively. The structures of the products were demonstrated by ir and nmr spectra. The ir bands, typical of the benzene nucleus, were noticed at $600-625\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The nmr spectrum revealed signals at δ 7.37 (1,4-benzene disubstituted nucleus), 4.48 (arylmethylene group) and 7.0 (protons on the phenothiazine nucleus).

The condensation of compound 3 with 4 was done at pH 5.5–6.0 using a non-protic bipolar solvent (tetramethylurea) as a medium for the reaction. The structure of compound 5 received support from uv spectra. An intense absorption maximum was noticed at 210–240 nm region, typical of 4. In the ir spectrum the absorption due to NH and OH groups were also noticed.

The diazonium salts of the amines were obtained by treatment with isoamyl nitrite in trifluoroacetic acid-dioxan³. After neutralization they were condensed with 5 furnishing the azo dyes (7). The azo dyes (7) obtained were coloured yellow, orange and red, and stable with good solubility.

Experimental

10-[(4'-Bromomethyl)benzil]phenothiazine (3) :
Method (a) : A mixture of phenothiazine (1, 1.99 g), DMA (1 ml), 30% aq. NaOH (10 ml), triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.2 g) and 1,4-bisbromomethylbenzene (2, 3.17 g) was stirred for 6 h at 50°. Then benzene (10 ml) was added, the organic phase washed with water, dried on $MgSO_4$, the solvent distilled under reduced pressure and the residue crystallized from benzene to yield 3 (49%) (Found : C, 62.71; H, 4.03; N, 3.92. $C_{20}H_{16}NSBr$ calcd. for : C, 62.82; H, 4.19; N, 3.66%).

Method (b) : A mixture of phenothiazine (1, 0.01 mol), thallium ethoxide (2.6 g), benzene (10 ml) and 1,4-bisbromomethylbenzene (2.9 g) was stirred for 40 h at 29°. It was then poured in ice-water and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was dried and crystallised to give 3 (94%).

Method (c) : A mixture of phenothiazine (1, 1.99 g), 1,4-bisbromomethylbenzene (2, 3.77 g), the solvent (DMA,

DMSO, HMPT) (10 ml) and DBU (0.2 g) was stirred for 6 h at 80°. The mixture was poured in ice-water, the organic phase extracted with benzene (10 ml) and washed with water to give 3 (96%).

Method (d) : A mixture of phenothiazine (1, 1.99 g), KOH (0.7 g), CTPB (0.2 g), acetone (10 ml) and 2 (3.77 g) was stirred for 48 h at 25°. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice-water, the organic phase extracted with benzene (10 ml) and washed with water to give 3 (62%).

Condensation of 4 with 3 : A mixture of 3 (7.69 g) dissolved in TMU (85 ml), sodium acetate (5 g) and water (18 ml) was cooled at 5–6°, then 4 (6.38 g) was added. The mixture was stirred for 3 h at 5°, then further 5 h at 25°. It was then poured in water (300 ml), brought to pH 4.8, filtered and the solid washed with water to yield 5 (85%) (Found : C, 57.94; H, 3.57; N, 4.39. $C_{28}H_{24}N_2O_7S_3$ calcd. for : C, 58.06; H, 3.87; N, 4.51%).

Coupling of the product 5 with diazonium salt 6 : The diazonium salt was brought to pH 4–5. A solution of 5 (6.2 g) in acetone-water (1 : 1; 200 ml) was added with stirring in cold. The stirring was continued at –5° for 2 h, then further 2 h at 15°. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and ether. The nitrogen content of the condensation compounds with diazonium salt of aniline, *p*-methoxyaniline, *o*-chloroaniline, *o*-aniline sulphonic acid and *p*-toluidine was found to be 7.62; 7.34; 7.23; 6.92; 7.42; $C_{36}H_{28}N_4O_7S_3$; $C_{37}H_{30}N_4O_8S_3$; $C_{36}H_{27}N_4O_7S_3Cl$; $C_{36}H_{28}N_4O_{10}S_4$; $C_{37}H_{30}N_4O_7S_3$ calcd. for : 7.73; 7.42; 7.38; 6.96; 7.58%.

The close amount of the azote that the azo dyes contain is due to the very large molecular mass of compounds 7.

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